

Re-Visiting Rumi and Iqbal on Self-Enhancement for Social Responsibility

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Abstract—The background of this study is the great degree of stress that the world is experiencing today, internationally among the countries, within a community among people, and even individually within one's own self. The significance of the study is the attempt to find a solution of this stress in the philosophy of the olden times of Jalaluddin Rumi and comparatively recently of that of Allama Iqbal. The methodology adopted in this paper is firstly exploration of the perspectives of these philosophers that are being consolidated by a number of psychic and spiritual experts of today, who are being widely read but less followed. This paper further goes on presenting brief life sketches of Rumi and Iqbal. It expounds the key concepts proposed by them and the social change that was resulted in the times of the two above mentioned metaphysical philosophers. It is further amplified that with the recent advancements, in both metaphysics and the physical sciences, the gap between the two is closing down. Both Rumi and Iqbal emphasized their common essence. The old time's concepts, postulates, and philosophies are hence once again becoming valid. The findings of this paper are that the existence of human empathy, affection and mutual social attraction among humans is still valid. The positive inner belief system that dictates our thoughts and actions is vital. As a conclusion, empathy should enable us solving our problems collectively. We need to strengthen our inner communication system, to listen to the messages that come to our inner-selves. We need to get guidance and strength from them. We need to value common needs and purposes collectively to achieve results. Spiritual energy among us is to be harnessed and utilized. Connectivity is to be recognized to unify and strengthen ties among people. Mutual bonding at small and large group levels is to be employed for the survival of the disadvantaged, and sustainability of the empowering trends. With the above guidelines, hopefully, we can define a framework towards a brave and happy new humane world.

Keywords—Belief system, connectivity, human empathy, inner-self, mutual bonding, spiritual energy.

I. INTRODUCTION

THERE is a need to reduce stress that exists today; internationally among the countries, within people, and even individually within one's own self [1], [2]. A solution in terms of enhancement of inner self geared towards social responsibility lies in the philosophy of Jalaluddin Rumi and that of Allama Iqbal whose teachings are being pursued by a number of psychic and spiritual experts of today. It is worth the while to study life sketches of Rumi and Iqbal, the key concepts proposed by them and the social change that resulted in the times of the two above mentioned metaphysical philosophers. With the recent advancements, in both metaphysics and the physical sciences, the gap between the two is closing down. It is time to unify the two faculties of

thought to work together to meet the common objectives, and to explore the old times concepts, postulates and philosophies that are once again becoming valid.

II. SOLUTIONS FOR OLDEN TIMES

Jalaluddin Rumi

Jalaluddin Rumi [3] born in 1207 in a family of theologians in Balkh, was a great man of metaphysics. He shifted to Baghdad under threats of the Mongols, and finally settled in Konya in the reign of Seljuks. Jalaluddin Rumi [4] promoted the immense powers of the inner self and practically infused a belief system that brought about significant social change in those times. He suggested that man has tremendous powers – spiritual powers inside himself. He also suggested that man has a connection to Almighty within man's own self. This was something new [5]. It was a great step forward in metaphysics. Jalaluddin Rumi died in 1273. This was the period when the Christians were fighting against Muslims – the Crusades. Crusades had been going on for 200 years. Jalaluddin Rumi was an initiator in diffusing the crusades. Crusades were brought to an abrupt end. The last crusade was fought in 1291. Within this short period of time, Rumi's concept of Christianity, Islam and Judaism being very close to each other worked very well. Jalaluddin Rumi was an interfaith man [6].

There are a number of concepts put forward by Rumi. One of them is that the Almighty dwells within man's inner self. If man wanted to search for the Almighty, he needed to look into within his own self. This was a great direction which Rumi gave. Then, there is another postulate, put forward by Rumi, that is, 'belief within one's own inner self ultimately manifests itself into reality' [7]-[9]. Apparently, it looked very strange, but there have been instances in history to support this viewpoint, as to how belief system works to create effects. This phenomenon has not been valued as much in the world of physical science. Yet, it has been duly appreciated in the science of mind, that if one has a strong belief within his mind in something, the reality does get attracted to it.

Role in Ending of Crusades

Rumi singlehandedly played a strong role in ending the crusades, in spite of having no power in his hand, no armies of his own, no guns, except belief. He spread that belief around [10], [11]. There were Muslim warlords, and there were Christian warlords, who were fighting against each other. He started writing letters to Muslim warlords and to the Christian warlords, telling them to find sense and stop fighting against each other, as there was not much difference between them as, 'water is water, no matter from which tap do you drink it'. He

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proposed that the Christian warlords should marry their sons or daughters to Muslim warlords' sons or daughters. He started proposing intermarriages. People thought it was not anyway workable, Rumi could not be serious, or he had his senses lost. But a time came, when one Christian warlord responded. He was ready to marry his daughter to a Muslim warlord's son. Rumi then spread this proposal to the Muslim warlords. There, one Muslim warlord was one, who agreed. Soon, the intermarriages started to occur. The crusades were abruptly ended. This was a place in Konya in Turkey. Suddenly people believed that there is not much difference, they were all human beings.

In 1291, the last crusade ended. In the last crusade, the decision that took place is still valid today. Jerusalem was made open to all three religions. Even today, there are three entrances. Muslims take one entrance, Christians take another and Jews can take yet another. This is how wars could be ended.

Allama Iqbal

Allama Iqbal [9] was born in 1877 in Sialkot in a poor family in the times of British Raj. He received early Islamic education and later western philosophy in UK and Germany, went through the times the World War I, rose to much cherished poet and philosopher of freedom movement in India [12]. He addressed to the immense powers of the inner self [13], and practically brought about a significant social change, while his own personal life had been suffering. 1914 has been an important year, because Allama Iqbal's mother died in this year. In the same year, Allama Iqbal's wife Karim Bibi died. Allama Iqbal married Sardar Begum and Mukhtar Begum. Right in the middle of turmoil, pressures and tensions going on in the mind of Allama Iqbal, his scholarly works carried immense message of the heights to which the inner self of man could rise, and thus bring about social change. In 1915, his work 'Israr e Khudi' came up, which earned him the title of 'Sir' from the British later in 1923. 1914 is also the year of start of the world war. The two enemy countries were England and Germany. Allama Iqbal happened to be in both these two countries. He spent time in Germany as well as in England. One can imagine the mind set of Allama Iqbal, when the war started. For serving the cause of freedom movement in India, Allama Iqbal joined Anjamine Hamayat e Islam, and rose to the position of General Secretary in 1919. In 1924, his wife 'Mukhtar Begum' died. She died in child birth, and his son 'Javed Iqbal' was born to 'Sardar Begum'. In 1926, he was elected in the Punjab Legislative Assembly. In 1928, he joined the Muslim League and left the National Liberation League. In 1930, he presided over the famous Muslim League Convention, and gave the idea of an independent state for Muslims of India [14]. These facts are recalled here, just to give a picture of the life of Allama Iqbal, when the book 'Baal e Jibril' came up, which contained a short piece titled 'Harf e Raaz' meaning 'the Secret', that is the subject of study of this paper.

In 1930, his father Shaikh Noor Muhammad died. In 1929-30, he lectured in Madras and Hyderabad on the

Reconstruction of Religious thoughts in Islam [15]. In 1931, he attended the 2nd Round Table Conference in London, and in 1932, he attended the 3rd Round Table Conference, which ended in no decisions. Anyway, he met Mussolini in Italy. He visited Qurtaba Mosque in Spain, and his famous poem 'Masjid-e Qurtaba' came along [16]. In 1933, he visited Afghanistan. He was invited by the King of Afghanistan, when his famous poem 'Mussafir' came along.

In 1933, he contracted a strange throat disease. His physical ailments, in fact, had been developing over a few years; like asthma, eyes, renal colon, kidneys and heart. So, his health started falling down. In 1935, Sardar Begum died. She was buried in Bibi Pak Daman. 1935 is also a very explosive year; earthquake of Quetta, Government of India Act, Communal Award, and it was a turmoil for the Muslim political parties.

Now, it is worthwhile to study Allama Iqbal's stay in Europe. In 1905, he traveled from Bombay to arrive at Trinity College Cambridge. He did a bachelor's degree there. During his bachelor's degree, he wrote a dissertation on Development of Metaphysics in Persia, on the basis of which, he got admission for a PhD at the Ludwig Maximilian's University Munich Germany. He spent a short time there and got a PhD on the subject of 'Development of Metaphysics in Persia' [17]. He then came back to London and was admitted to the Lincoln's Inn to obtain Bar at Law. He taught for a few months at the University College London, and came back to India in 1908 [18]-[20].

It is relevant to note the European philosophers of those days, from whom Allama Iqbal got inspirations during his stay in Europe. The first one is Fraulein Wegenast. She was a young lady who in fact taught Allama Iqbal the German language, and they held discussions on the European philosophers. Some of the philosophers were Goethe. Goethe has been a point of interest to Allama Iqbal to quite an extent, specially the Goethe's West- Östlicher Divan [21]. Allama Iqbal's book 'Payam e Mashriq' has reflections of it, and has been in fact an answer to this Divan.

Second is Schopenhauer. Schopenhauer's philosophy of 'Pure Will' has been a subject of interest to Allama Iqbal. Then comes Nietzsche [22]. Allama Iqbal agreed to Nietzsche on some of his philosophies but disagreed to some parts of his philosophies very vehemently. Bergson is a French philosopher whose concept of 'Godward-ness' has been interesting, and the reflections are there in Allama Iqbal's poetry. Then these physical scientists were there, in those days, when the concept of solidity of matter was questioned. Max Plank was one physical scientist who started engaging the concept of wave with matter, and really challenging the existence of solid matter. Einstein's theory was also a great blow to the force, mass acceleration concept of matter. The Newtonian concept was frustrated [23].

'Harf e Raaz': A Short Piece in 'Baal e Jibril'

'Baal e Jibril' [24] came about some times in 1935. It is second book of Allama Iqbal in Urdu. The first one is 'Baang e Dara', which came about in 1924. In the meantime, there

have been books in Persian like, *Israr e Khudi*, *Ramooz e Bekhudi*, *Payyam e Mashriq*, *Zaboore e Ajam*, *Javed Nama*, and in English the *Reconstruction of Religious Thought in Islam* [15]. The concepts and philosophies of Allama Iqbal can become clear in the study of these books [25]-[27].

Concepts

The concepts of Allama Iqbal can be summarily noted from one single short poetic piece 'Harf e Raaz' meaning 'A Word of Secret' [26] in the collection 'Baal e Jibril', probably written in 1920s. Only in 9 verses, the short piece describes how messages come into man's inner self, and the state of mind in which these messages can be picked up. There is the instant communication system which spreads these messages. These messages are greatly empowering. The force of ego reminds us that it is the man's job to build a better world. Above all, the answers to the world problems rest in Rumi's teachings. It is because of his thoughts that apparently meek man can have immense vigor and strength.

'Harf e Raaz': The Secret

Allama Iqbal's 9 verses of 'Harf e Raaz – the Secret' can be elaborated, verse by verse in the following:

1. 'It is the state of 'ecstasy' that opens the 'secret' before you. You need the power of instant communication to spread the word around'.

It is a state of ecstasy or 'an obsessive devotion' in which the secret message opens. It comes in a flash. It comes in the unconscious mind and does not stay there for long. Within a microsecond of a flash, it is to be interpreted, and brought to the conscious mind. An instant communication, breath of 'Jibril' [28] has to be built in, in order to understand the secret, translate the same into conscious mind language, and transfer and to other people. Allama Iqbal is here describing the incoming of intuition, understanding it and communicating it around. Similar expression for the process of intuition appears in [29].

2. 'Stars have no autonomous powers to foretell your destiny. Man has more autonomous power to fix his own destiny'.

The stars have no autonomous powers to foretell one's destiny. The lines of one's palm have no autonomous way to tell or foretell about one's destiny. Iqbal warns not to believe in such superstitions. He says, in fact, man has more autonomous powers. Man has been bestowed with tremendous autonomous powers. He can fix his own destiny. One gets these powers by looking into one's own self, trying to understand what messages are coming, and applying those messages into one's actions, one has extensive powers. These are spiritual powers. These are the powers that people have not fully utilized.

3. 'Life is the ability to listen to your inner messages. You do this by focusing on your thoughts and visions. Fears, doubts and wobblings kill this ability, your ego, and that is in fact the end of life'.

Allama Iqbal calls for deep concentration and focus on

thoughts and vision. If one does not have deep concentration or focus on one's own thoughts and vision, then one's life is nothing but wasted in chaos. That is no life. Life in fact is thrilling. Life in fact is vigorous. Life in fact is full of activity. That vigor and power one can only have, by concentrating on the thoughts and vision. If one drowns one's self in wobbling thoughts, fears and apprehensions, and if one gets one's self bogged down in such things, then it is no life. Then nothing can be expected as any results. Similar expression is found in recent times in [30].

4. 'Self-drive has a strange pleasure. It inflates you. Nature has a certain purpose behind it'.

Iqbal is talking of those people whose ego is alive. Self-drive is a strange pleasure. It inflates one up in the air. One is able to deliver great jobs. Those great abilities and powers can be obtained by searching within one's self, assembling one's powers, and discovering the right path. When, one gets the direction, then to go along with it.

5. 'People who pick up the messages, lead great lives. They perform great jobs. They have clear conscience. They have high self-esteem. They have a pleasurable occupancy. Worldly wealth and worldly apprehensions have no values before them'.

Allama Iqbal is referring to the looks of those energized people; a clear conscience, high self-esteem, and pleasurable occupation. The occupation that is chosen must be pleasurable. For people who are destined to deliver great jobs, the worldly wealth and the worldly apprehensions have no value. It is because they have picked up high targets for themselves. They have the energy. Energy has been pushed into them. They have searched within themselves, have strong belief in themselves and spread belief all around.

6. 'Transcendence of the Prophet is a lesson to man that the man hails above universe. Great heights you can attain. Just try to listen to the inner Will, and try to align your will with the inner Will'.

The concept of transcendence is there to infuse confidence, to make believe that man has immense powers, even to hail above universe. One gets these powers by looking deep into one's self, and have a creative mind, have an innovative mind, and belief in one's self. One can do virtually anything. The motivating power of transcendence, in today's world is described by Gohdes [31].

7. 'The messages of 'I say be, so it be' are coming from your inner self. Man has been chosen to fait accompli. The world is yet to be completed. Man has been chosen to do it'.

The message is, 'listen to your heart'; the inner voice of one's ego. It calls for moving on, and doing better and still better. This universe is not complete yet. Man has been assigned to complete this universe now. Man has been trying. Great scientists, great philosophers, poets and political leaders all have been trying. Man has been moving inch by inch, slowly and slowly progressing towards completeness. This is the dictate which comes from within one's self. This is ego.

This is the genetic kick coming out within one's self. The ego comes and says, 'I am the master of the universe, and I am entitled to avail the bounties of nature'. Why can't I reach the moon? Man tries, and he does reach the moon. The ego kick needs to be collectively utilized for the benefit of mankind. In recent years, a good deal of emphasis has been drawn on social responsibility that is based on spiritual energy, as described by Clamor [32], Humphrey et al. [33] and Hostenstein [34]. There is worth mentioning of the Social Accountability ISO Code SA8000 [35] that has come to shape.

8. 'The spiritual frame of Rumi has the solution to our woes. Get on with it, and build a better world. You are instead overwhelmed with the false spell of the West's selfish outwardly pursuits'.

Cure of all the woes of today lies in the flame that Jalaluddin Rumi kindled for mankind. Spells of conspiracies inflicted by a few for their selfish motives need to be collectively resisted. The solution has been proposed by Rumi. The solution of Rumi in today's world has been described by a number of contemporary authors such as Razia [36], Rumi Jr [37], Tompkins [38], Lewis [39], Can [40], and Schimmel [41].

9. 'The spiritual solution of Rumi has illuminated brightness in my eyes. It is with this that I can fill my pitcher with whole river Jaihun of gushing and turbulent water'.

Allama Iqbal says that he gets his vision from the illuminating thoughts of Rumi. It is because of Rumi that his thoughts have been invigorated. The message is that the spiritual energy within oneself can be so great that it can be equated to that of a bursting, gushing and turbulent river. In today's world the spiritual solutions are proposed by authors such as Dale [42], Clugston [43], Pimentel [44], Hugen [45], Brower [46], Cabot [47], and Constable [48].

III. NARROWING GAP BETWEEN METAPHYSICS AND PHYSICAL SCIENCES

The world today is divided among two groups: people who belong to physical sciences who do not value much of metaphysics and people of metaphysics who do not really have the analytical working of physical sciences. However, with the recent advancements in both metaphysics and the physical sciences, the gap between the two is closing down. The ideas of Rumi and Iqbal therefore have become worthy of study.

Glorious Instant Communication System

In the metaphysical world, there is the Archangel Jibril. There is a mention of 'Jibril' [28] in 'Harf e Raaz' as well. It may be noted that the role of Jibril is that of a messenger. It is the messenger who makes instant communication. As per the description given of 'Jibril' he is stretched from horizon to horizon. In the world of physical sciences, today, it is known that almost instant communication takes place. Interstellar gravity waves [75] and terrestrial waves [76] are phenomena by which almost instant communication can take place. These are later discoveries. It is to illustrate that the gap between

metaphysics and the physical sciences is closing down.

Exploring the Inner-Self

There has been a limitation with man's physical senses. The senses can see only the world that is outside the body. There has been no way by which inside of the body could be seen. Somewhere in the past, we started to probe into inside the body. Reading the pulse on the wrist, has been the first step. Reading body temperature, X-ray, CT scan, and EEG came about later. But again, these methods could see only the physical side of the human body. There is a lot of activity in our inner self that is still not captured yet. However, in metaphysics, there has been a long way of experiences by which people have been visualizing and discovering the secrets of our inner self [79].

Pre-scripted Messages in DNA

In biology, there is a genetic mystery within the living selves. The DNA is considered as the unit of life. There is a genetic code printed in the DNA. Right from the inception, the genetic code is there. It dictates the events which are going to follow afterwards. The road map, of the development within the living selves, their growth and function, is all set inside the DNA. Scientists did not know it before. The discovery came in 1953 when the structure of DNA was configured by James Watson. Then in 2001 the complete genetic map was decoded by Collins. This genetic map is a blue print. It has been given to human beings. They do not make it. As described by Clelland [49], there is a messenger RNA, which reads the genetic code and emits 'dictates' for the development and function there on. Then cells form groups together, in the form of organs. The coordination develops among the organs. Ultimately the whole body stands up on its own feet, starting from a mere group of gel like cells. It can be seen that there is a genetic code which is governing all this development.

Rise of Ego and the Ego Kick

The human development is a result of a genetic 'kick'. As described by Solms and Panksepp [50], it is the force in fact which develops into 'ego'. The dictates of our biology develops into human 'ego' as interpreted from [77]. The ego says, 'I am of value, I am authority, I am entitled to avail the bounties of nature, and if I say 'be' so it should be'. This is the ego which is bestowed to human beings. The ego which develops into human selves is the work of the DNA and the messenger RNA works beautifully well, within human selves.

Collective Ego and Connectivity

Now, from individual to individual, the interaction starts. The individual moves outwards and exchanges his thoughts ideas and concepts within other individuals. The individual starts having awareness of what is around him, what is his family, what is his tribe, and what is his community. The awareness progresses to the national level, and it grows onto the total humanity level. These feelings that are created within the individual's selves towards the community, the nationality and total humanity, are all connectivity [74]. The connectivity develops into the system. The work of the 'genetic kicks'

going up to collective levels, is marvelous. This is how pyramids were made. This is how the collective ego could be scientifically described [51].

Movement towards Better, Complete and Perfect World

It has been seen that individuals start interacting with each other, cooperating with each other and fighting with each other, and competing with each other. First the ego develops individually, and then it evolves into a 'collective ego'. This is how humanity moves forward collectively with this kick, to do a better world, moving on towards perfection [52].

How to Pick-up Inner Messages

Now the flow of messages has been tracked, it is important to learn how best these messages can be clearly received and comprehended.

(i) The First Rule

The first rule is to free one's mind from wobbling thoughts and mean desires. Various communities and various religions do it differently. But they all seem to follow this rule. A fully free mind and concentration of thoughts are the required.

(ii) The Second Rule

Then there is this second principal of how best one can pick up these messages. This is a state of ecstasy, or 'devotedness' one needs to get into. In order to open one's mind up, one must have a kind of 'obsession for search'. In such a state, messages come and are exposed. One then needs to align one's belief to that what is exposed.

(iii) The Third Rule

Now comes the most important rule. It is that 'beliefs' create 'reality'. This is the circle – beliefs, concepts, thoughts, actions, and results. The results reflect back onto the beliefs. This is the mechanism. Everything really, originates from beliefs. If one believes in something, then the reality emerges accordingly.

An example is that of Columbus, who discovered America. He had this belief that if he went across the Atlantic, he would reach land. Nobody was convinced that there was a land at the end of the ocean. What he found was a new continent. His belief produced results.

Another example is that of the Muslims of India, who were scattered into tribes. A belief was generated among them that they were together a nation. They got united and fought for a country of their own, that came into existence in the name of Pakistan. Allama Iqbal created this belief among the Muslims of India. Allama Iqbal knew that if he could create a belief in them, they would stand up and struggle, and one day they would get a country for themselves. This is how 'belief' is so important.

To prepare a nation to fight its troubles, a strong belief in its people has to be created and safeguarded. To destroy a nation, the belief of people among themselves is to be frustrated. This is how the propaganda warfare is done. When frustrated, people are unable to address to their problems.

Einstein on Intuition

Einstein says, 'The only real valuable thing in this world is intuition'. Einstein is considered as the greatest scientist of the century. He believes in intuition [53]. It is the intuitive power that we need to develop. Intuitive powers can be harnessed by concentration, prayers, ecstasy and 'devoted obsessions'.

I. Einstein on Energy Empowerment

According to Einstein, the basic reality is energy, and everything else is its embellishments. We need to match the frequency of what we want to obtain, with the frequency of this reality, and we are sure to get it [54].

IV. CONTEMPORARY SOLUTIONS IN PSYCHIC AND SPIRITUAL TERMS

There are a significant number of contemporary scholars, and practitioners who have carried forward Rumi's and Iqbal's thoughts and concepts, though on more secular and psychic levels, rather than traditional religious lines. Some of these workers are Clinton [55], El-Zein [56], Tun [57], Furlanetto [58], Catherine [59], Winston [60] and Yilmaz [80].

Only a random and short selection is quoted as below.

Justine Thorner

Justine Thorner is an American spiritual wellness expert, whose practice focuses upon the science of listening to the inner self. For this purpose, she recommends the broad steps such as: (a) Listen; (b) Start listening to yourself; (c) Live in the present mode; not in past, not in future, but in the present day; (d) Calm down; when the mind is calm, the connection is stronger; (e) Stop trying: stop being hectic or confused, stay relaxed; and (f) Be patient and meditate [61].

Rhonda Byrne

There is a book by Rhonda Byrne titled 'the Secret', the best seller, in 50 languages, 20 million copies of which have been sold. The entire theme of the book is derived from Rumi. In fact, Rumi is studied extensively in the contemporary world: Byrne [62], and Sanneh [63]. The theme of the book is how to make the universe obey you [64].

Rhonda Byrne an Australian born radio and TV producer released a film named 'The Secret' in 2006 which received tremendous applause all across the globe, followed by the book. In 2007, Rhonda was interviewed by Oprah Winfrey. The Time magazine declared Rhonda as among the 100 most influential persons in the world, ones who shaped our world. Another of her book 'the Power' came along in 43 languages, which became the New York Time's best seller. A third book was there, 'the Magic' in 2012, and a fourth one 'the Hero' in 2013. Rhonda Byrne's The Secret says, 'It may take a while for you to understand, but your thoughts hold the magical power to change your life just the way you are. The power of positive visualization is just what you need to start practice in life'. Rhonda Byrne's 'The Secret' serves as a cheat sheet to life. The book has transformed the lives of millions across the world. And what makes the book stand out from the rest is that it is not just another self-help book. The secret professed by

Rhonda is the Law of Attraction, which is really derived from Rumi, 'thoughts become things'. The message is to have positive thinking, to expect positive results. The thoughts seem to hold magical power to change one's life. The power of positive capitalization is one that is needed.

Oprah Winfrey

There is another person: Oprah Winfrey. She delivers program on TV. Her shows have been declared as the most viewed program of 1992. Oprah Winfrey is a psychic spiritual expert. Her entire programs rest on Rumi's philosophy [65].

In Super Soul Sunday [66], which got 3 times declared Emmy Award winner, Oprah Winfrey asks questions to today's top thinkers, teachers, and spiritual leaders. These questions pertain to some of life's biggest issues, and the answers carry most important lessons. Oprah continually stresses that one can have a direct connection within one's own self. Oprah Winfrey, born in Mississippi in a poor family in 1954, pursued her career as a media executive, actress, anchor, and producer. Her 'Oprah Winfrey Shows' were declared highest viewed shows from 1986 to 2011 [67]. She became the richest African American [68], and the first black multi-billionaire. Her salary crossed \$75m mark in 2013 and net assets reached \$2.9b in 2018. Sometimes, she is considered as the most influential person in the world. She acquired her spiritual inclinations drawn from Rumi. From 2007 onwards, Oprah Winfrey started organizing interview programs in the name of 'the Secret'. She professed a feeling experience and not a believing kind of experience.

On the solution of the problems prevalent today, of gun violence, climate change and economic and racial inequality, Oprah believes the biggest hurdle is 'misinformation' that has to stop. She proposes to adopt 'bold truth' as it was the saving grace [78].

As for the feeling kind of experiences, she narrated that one could ask questions to one's inner self in a state of deep concentration, then the answers start coming. The answers are compatible to one's own perceptual capabilities, and to the limits of the questions themselves. These are steps of awareness, going deeper and deeper in steps. Rumi also said something similar. He said, 'What you seek is seeking you'. Oprah quotes an instance of certain Karen Cavanagh [69], who broke her neck and got a brain injury, and the doctors thought she would not survive. In her stance, words of Rumi rang into her mind, which gave her hope. She recovered. She started studying sufism, meditation and remained a devoted person all rest of her life [70].

Law of Attraction

According to the Law of Attraction, 'what goes inside a person; similar from outside gets attracted to it' [71]. It is like sitting in a restaurant, placing an order, and be at maximum served with that order. In regard to personal self enhancement, the law of attraction calls for attaining characteristics, within one's own self such that one's personality acts like a magnet. One's goals would then be automatically attracted.

V. SUGGESTED MODEL THROUGH A STRUCTURED FRAMEWORK

The development of human empathy, affection and mutual social attraction among humans is suggested through the following framework.

Power of Inner Belief System

Constructing and spreading positive inner belief system would reflect positively on the thoughts and actions, thus enabling collectively to solve the problems.

Power of Connectivity

The inter communication system needs to be strengthened. This is a path towards unifying and strengthening the bond among people.

Listening to Your Inner Self

The messages that come into the inner-selves are needed to be given concentrated attention. These messages are there to fetch guidance and strength. These messages inculcate common values and purpose in life. These messages enable collectively to achieve peace and comfort.

Power of Spiritual Energy

Spiritual energy among is to be harnessed and utilized.

Mutuality

The survival of the disadvantaged groups as well the security of the empowering trends, both are served by induction of mutual bonding [72], [73].

VI. CONCLUSION

The solution to the problems facing today, lies in the metaphysical philosophy of the olden times of Jalaluddin Rumi and comparatively recently of that of Allama Iqbal. These are being consolidated by a number of present day psychic and spiritual experts. The expounded key concepts can bring about the needed enhancement of the self and a sense of social responsibility. Metaphysics is becoming more convincing as an instrument of change, as the gap with the physical sciences is closing down. Its philosophies are hence once again becoming valid. The existence of human empathy, affection and mutual social attraction among humans can form a strong instrument of change. Constructing a positive inner belief system and dictating our thoughts and actions, can enable us collectively to solve the problems. Spiritual energy raises the level of mutual bonding, connectivity and helps to bring the disadvantaged people closer to the privileged class. With the above guidelines, hopefully one can define a framework towards a happy and connected new humane world.

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